

Analysis of Green Intellectuals, Environmentally Friendly and Green Competitive Behaviors on the Advantages of Green Motivation at PT Dian Daya Dinamika

Wenny Desty Febrian^{1*}, Yanthy Herawaty Purnama², Indra Sani³

^{1,2}Universitas Dian Nusantara, Jakarta

³ITB Asia, Malang

Corresponding Author: Wenny Desty Febrian wenny.desty.febrian@undira.ac.id

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ABSTRACT

In today's industrial world, the environment functions as a resource for the survival and sustainability of industrial activities themselves as well as a place to live or stand. Companies such as PT Dian Daya Dinamika, as well as the community and government, are paying attention and taking serious action on these environmental issues. Regarding the state of the environment and depleting of natural resources, the company has made a significant contribution. which got worse. Businesses should encourage green production in their operations, but a green environment does not necessarily require zero pollution. This research aims to examine the behavior of environmentally friendly employees towards green motivation. To achieve green competitive advantage (Y), manufacturing companies need green intellectual (X1) and environmentally friendly behavior (X2) in their operations as well as green motivation (X3). This research uses a literature review method. The output was submitted to an international journal, namely Copernicus

INTRODUCTION

Currently, tourism is the most interesting thing for local and international tourists to visit (Ansari et al., 2021). Two years earlier, the impact of Covid 19 caused the tourism industry to stop functioning; However, after the COVID-19 period ended, tourism emerged as a major attraction. (Aluko et al., 2021). Each region has a different attraction in terms of tourism, the environment is not only a place to live but also a resource for the continuity and continuity of industrial activities themselves (Amoako, 2020). However, without realizing it, the environment is being damaged by the company's activities (Asiaei et al., 2022). Company waste and activities have a negative impact and cause damage to the environment (Astuti & Wahyuni, 2018). Water, land, and air pollution, landfilling of waste that exceeds capacity, global warming, damage to the ecosystem, the emergence of various diseases, floods, and other natural disasters are examples of damage that has been done to the environment. The worst example is the Earth which is on the verge of destruction (Anwar et al., 2020).

The environmental issues above have become very serious problems, and the community and government also provide serious attention and action regarding this matter (Asadi et al., 2020). Companies have a big contribution to make regarding the increasingly deteriorating natural environment. A green environment does not always have to be zero pollution, industry must encourage green production in its activities (Beineiveinei & Buonomo, 2020).

Several research findings reveal factors that can impact both directly and indirectly on corporate growth and competitive advantage, namely: impact on green environmental performance. i and idiosyncrasies compete according to the business and objectives of the organization (Chaudhary , 2020).

While research is related to the global intellectual capital factor, the research related to global intelligence capital is influenced by motivation, innovation, and innovation, which will later create a tourism sector that has good competitiveness (A'yuini & Muiafi, 2010).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Author and Year

Alam & Islam (2021)

Definitions

Greiein Competitivei Advantagei has been described as a condition of innovation that cannot be imitated by others where the company takes a position over ecological management or sustainable innovation.

Widiyati & Muirwaningsari (2021)

Greiein Competitivei Advantagei Greiein Competitivei Advantagei is a situation where a company reaches an advantage compared to competitors' companies in market competition.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHODOLOGY

The purpose of writing this article is to review and summarize the literature review related to the implementation of employee engagement in multinational companies so that they know what factors can be effectively used to increase employee engagement through various methods, other career factors, and transactions. management, Recruitment, and Organizational Commitment, researchers attempt to read, analyze, and summarize literature reviews from various journals and other related information sources to determine a strategy to implement effective employee engagement in an organization. This study uses a literature review approach to achieve the research objectives. The mini-assessment of employee engagement is conducted by reading and analyzing several peer-reviewed journal articles. This research method is a literature review that compares several existing theories and previous studies. To obtain the information and data necessary for this work, the following data collection methods are used: Documents/Library, ie. a data collection technique for researching documents related to the researched problem. The data analysis method of this study uses the literature review analysis method using an inductive reasoning model. The analysis process is carried out using a data analysis technique, which is content analysis. In other words, a detailed description of data and context, their nature, characteristics, content, reasoning, and the use of inductive logic to draw conclusions.

RESULTS

Several previous literature shows that green competitive advantage is supported by determining predictors such as; factors of Green Human Resource Management, Green Marketing, Green Intellectual Capital, and so on (Gupta & Gupta, 2020). This research uses several independent variables to explain the relationship and influence on the creation of Green Competitive Advantage for manufacturing companies that are the object of research (Hadjri et al., 2020).

Employee environmentally friendly behavior is referred to as Organizational Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCBEi) and is a voluntary individual action that leads to effective environmental performance within the organization (Purnama et al., 2021).

Based on the 2022 Green Industry Report, research indicates that as many as 55% of consumers in 60 countries pay more for environmentally friendly products (Al-Gasawneh et al., 2021). At least 71% of Americans, including researchers, think about the environment when shopping. From current green business practices, green functional areas such as green human resource management are balanced (Majid Eit et al., 2022).

Competitiveness is one of the most important advantages for an organization, every competition must be an effort to create a new competitive environment or dimension, if the competition goes through competition it will create a new way of playing. Intuition can survive in a more competitive environment, the implementation of research requires implementing strategies, which are formulated previously through internal and external analysis (Guipita & Guipita, 2020).

A competitive strategy is the search for a desirable competitive position in an industry because of the fundamentals of where competition occurs (Hadjri et al., 2020).

DISCUSSION

Motivation to win the competition is needed by manufacturing companies to continue to survive in business, management and employees have an important role in fostering motivation to keep the company environment green so that they can enjoy work and success for a long time (Ahmed et al., 2021).

Green intelligence is something that is important for an employee in a company to achieve superior green motivation in the company. Environmentally friendly behavior is of course also very necessary to be able to increase the closeness and cohesiveness of employees in a company, this will of course have a very positive influence on achieving superior green motivation. Likewise with green competitiveness, green competitive factors will greatly support the achievement of the vision and mission aimed at by a company, especially for achieving green motivational excellence.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This research suggests that companies can improve all the variables in this research in order to increase their green competitive advantage

FURTHER STUDY

for future researchers to be able to add variables that match the dependent variable.

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